

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING WORDS WITH ANTI-MEAN MEANING IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga zid ma'noli so'zlarni o'rgatishning metodik jihatlari yoritilgan. Zid ma'noli so'zlarni o'rgatish orqali o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirish, tafakkur doirasini kengaytirish, mustaqil fikrlashga yo'naltirish usullari ko'rib chiqilgan. Ushbu jarayonda vizual materiallar, didaktik o'yinlar, integratsiyalashgan yondashuv va interaktiv metodlar qo'llanilishining afzalliklari misollar asosida tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: zid ma'noli so'zlar, boshlang'ich ta'lim, metodika, og'zaki nutq, lug'at boyligi, didaktik o'yinlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методические аспекты обучения антонимам учащихся начальной школы. Были рассмотрены методы увеличения словарного запаса учащихся, расширения их кругозора и поощрения самостоятельного мышления путем обучения антонимам. На примерах проанализированы преимущества использования наглядных материалов, дидактических игр, комплексного подхода и интерактивных методов в этом процессе.

Ключевые слова: антонимы, начальное образование, методика, устная речь, лексика, дидактические игры.

Abstract: The article discusses the methodological aspects of teaching antonyms to primary school students. Methods for increasing students' vocabulary, expanding their thinking, and directing them to independent thinking through teaching antonyms are considered. The advantages of using visual materials, didactic games, an integrated approach, and interactive methods in this process are analyzed based on examples.

Keywords: antonyms, primary education, methodology, oral speech, vocabulary, didactic games.

Antonyms are lexical units that are opposite in meaning and are an important tool for increasing language proficiency. Teaching such words in primary school is one of the main factors in expanding students' vocabulary, developing their ability to express their thoughts clearly, and developing logical thinking. In the educational process, it is important for students not only to memorize antonyms, but also to teach them to use them correctly and in everyday life.

Main part:

1. The importance of antonyms

Antonyms develop students' abilities to compare and contrast events and clarify ideas. Learning such words also has a positive effect on the student's overall thinking.

2. Teaching methodologies and approaches

a) visual methods:

Pictures, slides, and flashcards make it easier to remember words with opposite meanings. For example: big - small, fast - slow, hot - cold.

b) didactic games:

Games such as "Find the Opposite", "Say the Pair of Words", and "Which One is Wrong?" increase students' interest in the lesson.

c) practical exercises:

Exercises such as finding the opposite of a word, constructing sentences with opposite words, and searching for antonyms in the text strengthen students' independence.

d) role-playing games:

Dialogue-based exercises (for example: "Today it is hot - yesterday it was cold") help the student use words in speech.

e) integrated approach:

Antonyms can be taught in conjunction with other subjects (mathematics, natural sciences) to provide a deeper understanding of their meaning.

f) information and communication technologies (ICT):

Interactive textbooks, slide presentations, and online games increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

Conclusion: When advanced pedagogical technologies, game methods, visual aids and integrated approaches are used in the process of teaching antonyms in primary grades, this will serve the development of students' vocabulary, thinking and communication culture. In this regard, the teacher should not be a provider of knowledge, but a guide who develops the student's speech and mental activity.

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